

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

GINA I. CABALLERO, LPT, MAEd

Instructor I

Partido State University

gina.caballero@parsu.edu.ph

“TOO NEAR YET SO FAR: WHEN WE LAND THAT JOB”

As we became mature, we realized that everything is not easy and that Barbie dolls are no longer the goal, just like when we were little kids wanting to own beautiful, skinny Barbie dolls with many clothes to wear.

As we aged, life became harder, and happiness, contentment, and fulfillment became so hard to reach. There will be a lot of struggles we have to face before we can achieve the dream we always want to have.

After college graduation, one aspires to have a job to escape from the underestimation other people impliedly told us about. When we land the first job that helps us escape that first reality, we aspire to land a job that will make us stay longer. When we land that job, we aspire to have a job that is near our place so that we could easily go home without hassling with the heavy traffic.

When we land that job, we aspire to the job that will fulfill our wants that somewhat align with our capacity. When we land that job, we want to go with the job that will give us the pride and honor that we belonged to that institution. When we land that job, we want to look for a job that will give us the benefit that will help us not only for ourselves but for our family. A job that will be with us in times of hardships and struggles and support us until the day that we separate from them. That is the goal.

As we go along with our aspirations, we are becoming so greedy for success that we forget to live our lives, that we forget to breathe, pause, and relax. It was only during the time when everything seemed like it was paused—that is, the time that is indirectly saying, take your time because life is not a race. There will be hindrances that will come our way, but they are only challenges we need to overcome to reach the exciting part we have always dreamed of. If it is for you, it will come and find you. Just be thankful for where you are now and be patient while you wait.